

A PRACTICAL ANIMAL DETECTION AND COLLISION AVOIDANCE SYSTEM USING COMPUTER VISION TECHNIQUES

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Abstract:

Transportation departments around the world deal with an ever-increasing number of animal-vehicle collisions as they cause thousands of human and animal fatalities along with billions in economic losses each year. This is one of the few areas of transportation where safety is not improving. As more roads are built, the areas that animals inhabit shrink, causing more collisions between vehicles and animals. Human deaths and injuries, animal deaths and injuries, and the material costs of these accidents highlight the need to address this problem. Through this paper, new research directions and combinations of technologies suitable to cover research gaps are introduced.

Keywords — **Image Classification, Deep Learning, Artificial Intelligence, object matching, edge-based matching, skeleton extraction.**

I. INTRODUCTION

Updated knowledge about different animals will influence our study of species management in the ecosystem. Manual identification of animals and their characteristics remains a manual and costly and time-consuming task. Therefore, we propose that such identification and classification can be done with maximum accuracy using deep learning neural network techniques. The main purpose of using neural network deep learning techniques is that the neural network framework can automatically learn

from the training images by extracting features from the images and predict the test images with effective accuracy. This aims to reduce manual effort and cost and conserve and preserve the wildlife ecosystem. We will show that such animal detection can be done using deep convolution neural network frameworks with high accuracy.

Data Mining is the process of identifying and discovering trends and patterns in large data sets, which is a combination of multiple fields that include machine learning, statistics, and database systems. It

focuses on extracting information from large data sets and transforming it into an interpretable and understandable format for future use. It is mainly used for data preprocessing, data classification and categorization. Image classification analyzes, identifies and discovers several image features and organizes image data into different categories using several algorithms. It mainly uses two characteristic stages of processing: training and testing. In the training phase, a unique identity of each category is obtained. In the testing stage, these novel personalities are utilized to group the picture information into classes. A neural network is a series of algorithms that analyze a set of data and recognize underlying relationships in the data. They are the drivers of deep learning. Deep Learning is an artificial intelligence technology that is used to process larger data sets and is mainly used in decision making and image classification and pattern generation. It is a subset of machine learning that consists of networks capable of training by unsupervised learning from unstructured data. The reason we chose to use deep learning is that it is one of the only methods that can overcome the challenges of feature extraction by learning several different features from large data sets by itself without much effort on the part of the programmer. For the most part, in an acknowledgment framework, when an info picture is given, highlights are removed from the picture. The network uses these to train from the training data and organizes the data into classes. The knowledge gained from the training is used to predict the test data based on the features and classify them accordingly. A recognition system can be used with identification and verification. Identification is where a given image is compared to all other images to create a ranked list of matches, while Verification is where a given image is compared and the animal's identity is confirmed or disproved.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

An increasing area of the Earth's surface has been transformed by human activity, which is changing wildlife populations, habitats and behavior. More seriously, many wild species on Earth have become extinct, and many species are being introduced into new areas where they can disrupt both natural and human systems. Wildlife monitoring is therefore essential as it provides researchers with evidence to

inform conservation and management decisions to conserve diversity.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

Animal detection is useful in preventing animal vehicle accidents and will increase the safety of people and wildlife, recognizing large animals before they enter the road and warning drivers with audible and visual signals. This also helps in saving farm crops from animals. In this project there is an overview of different techniques for object detection and for object identification as animal techniques such as object matching, edge-based matching, skeleton extraction. After the survey, the most suitable method for animal detection is selected and the effectiveness is measured. The proposed system has a low rate of false positives and false negatives. The existing background subtraction study was performed with the assumption of a static background. Many background segmentation models use a base image that consists only of the background. The dynamic background challenge is addressed by considering the local segmentation sensitivity using pixel-level feedback loops of the video images.

DISADVANTAGE

Solid and proficient article division and identification require the expulsion of supposition about fixed foundations. For division in powerful pictures, there are different focuses to consider, i.e., assessment of scenes at pixel level, spatial setting, diagram cut at region level and closer view foundation ID at successive level, and so on. This is hard to carry out in genuine world.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The aim of the proposed algorithm is to implement animal classification by using two deep learning neural network frameworks – CNN and Faster RCNN and highlight the importance of deep learning technology in classification problems. The proposed calculation is comprising of five principal steps.

- Image collection
- Data set splitting
- Train CNN and Faster RCNN algorithm
- Order utilizing CNN and Quicker RCNN calculation

RCNN calculation

ADVANTAGES

- The arrangement done utilizing deep learning models.
- The accuracy of classification is high.

V. RESULTS

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this project we came across many animal detection systems that have their advantages and disadvantages. Yet in a country like India, there is no practical implementation of such systems despite the increasing number of stray animal accidents. Future research needs to thrive to develop a system that will be able to detect animals during the day, night and also in fog. None of the existing systems promised to detect animals in foggy weather. Additionally, in urban environments, most AVCs occur when dogs or cows hit a vehicle, so we need to focus on detecting animals like dogs and cows instead of moose or giraffes.

Although our proposed system can detect animals (cow) on roads and highways and also alert drivers, it also has some limitations. The proposed system can detect an animal up to a distance of 20 meters only when the vehicle is stationary. The system can prevent a vehicle from colliding with an animal when driving at a speed of 30 to 35 km/h. When exceeding this speed, even if an animal is detected, there is not enough time to prevent the animal from colliding with the vehicle.

Some means or method of increasing the detection distance of the animal from the camera-mounted vehicle must be implemented to give the driver enough time to brake or take any other action to avoid a collision, which can be resolved using high-resolution cameras or radar. No effort was made to detect animals during the night, which is expected in our future scope of study and research.

In the system proposed above, the grids are only on colour images. Therefore, in the future we want to work on grayscale images that are entered as input to the system. We would like to extend the system so that the accuracy of the predicted test image is literally high. The above system is intended for single label classification only. That is why we want to work on the classification of more brands in the future.

VII. REFERENCE

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